

The Little Mermaid: Fiction or Fact?

Margaret A Uchefuna^{1*}, Kenechukwu K Iloh², Chukwukelue N Uchefuna³

¹Pediatrics, Woodhull Medical Center, New York, USA

²Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu, Nigeria

³Surgery, University of Nigeria Teaching Hospital, Enugu, Nigeria

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***Corresponding author:** Margaret A Uchefuna, Pediatrics, Woodhull Medical Center, New York, USA

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ABSTRACT

Sirenomelia is a caudal regression disorder characterized by fusion of the lower limbs into a single piece. This causes the infant to look like a mermaid hence it is also known as mermaid syndrome. A baby was delivered at 35 weeks gestational age through emergency cesarean section, to a 28-year old woman who began prenatal care in her third trimester. At birth, the baby had fusion of the lower limbs with a common skin covering, fusion of the feet giving a flipper-like, common foot, and absent external genitalia. APGAR score was four in the first minute, with no improvement despite resuscitative measures and the baby was certified dead twenty minutes later. Cultural beliefs precluded autopsy. The outcome of Sirenomelia is guarded; as such, an ethical dilemma exists for the benefit of treating such patients and the quality of life even after treatment. Knowledge of this peculiar syndrome is important to dissipate cultural myths, free affected families from stigmatization and encourage them to consent to autopsy for further research whenever the condition occurs.

INTRODUCTION

Sirenomelia, also known as mermaid syndrome, is a rare congenital abnormality characterized by defective development of the lower spine and the lower limbs.^[1] This gives the fetus the semblance of a mermaid, with the upper half of the fetus looking like the body of a human and the lower half looking like the tail of a fish. There is no ethnic predilection, but there is a greater propensity for fetuses with sirenomelia to be male and male to female ratio is estimated to be 3:1.^[1,2]

The incidence of sirenomelia is 0.8-1 case/100,000 births^[2] and less than 400 cases of sirenomelia have been reported globally,^[3] with the first case in 1542.^[4] Only a handful of patients with sirenomelia survived beyond the neonatal period,^[1] the longest surviving patient dying in 2016, at the age of 27 years.^[5] The mermaid syndrome is strongly associated with maternal diabetes and almost a quarter of fetuses with this anomaly will have mothers with diabetes.^[6,7] Other possible risk factors include tobacco use, exposure to retinoic acid or heavy metals and maternal age younger than 20 years or older than 40 years.^[8]

CASE PRESENTATION

A late preterm baby was delivered at 35 weeks gestational age through emergency lower segment cesarean section, to a 28-year old woman, gravida four, para three with three living and healthy children. She began prenatal care in her third trimester. The baby's parents were unrelated and the mother had no occupational risk factor, or personal or family history of diabetes. She did not drink alcohol or smoke cigarettes before or during pregnancy.

A week before delivery, the baby's mother had spontaneous vaginal bleeding associated with intermittent lower abdominal pain. Prenatal ultrasound revealed a live fetus in a breech presentation with grade 3 placenta previa and oligohydramnios. She received prophylactic intravenous antibiotics and dexamethasone but due to progressive fetal bradycardia, a cesarean section was done.

At birth, the baby had morphological abnormalities like fusion of the lower limbs with a common skin covering, fusion of the feet giving a flipper-like, common foot, and absent external genitalia as shown in [Figures 1 and 2](#).

Figure 1: Fusion of lower limbs into a single stump with a common skin covering, absent external genitalia.

Figure 2: Fusion of the feet giving a flipper-like, common foot.

APGAR score was four in the first minute, with no improvement despite resuscitative measures and the baby was certified dead twenty minutes later. Cultural beliefs precluded autopsy.

DISCUSSION

The distinctive feature of sirenomelia is the union of both lower limbs which may be associated with bony defects like rotation of the fibula, absence of the lower spine, and abnormalities of the upper limbs and internal organs.^[1] Two important hypotheses can account for the pathogenesis of mermaid syndrome: vitelline artery steal hypothesis and defective blastogenesis hypothesis. The vitelline artery steal reroutes blood flow from the embryo to the placenta resulting in growth arrest of the caudal region in the fetus^[9] while defective blastogenesis disrupts angiogenesis, truncating growth and development of the lower body organs and limbs.^[4]

The presentation of sirenomelia is variable and may range from single bones to two distinct but fused bones to entirely absent bones.^[7] A classification of sirenomelia into seven types was made by Stocker and Heifetz, on the basis of the presence or absence of lower limb bones and the extent of their fusion: class I: all lower limb bones present; class II: one fibula absent; class III: both fibulae absent; class IV: partially fused femurs, fused fibulae; class V: partially fused femurs, absent fibulae; class VI: one femur and one tibia absent; class VII: one femur and both tibiae absent.^[8] The exact classification of our patient could not be ascertained as parents declined further investigations and autopsy. Potter facies are also occasionally found, due to coexisting oligohydramnios, and are characterized by large, low-set ears, prominent epicanthic folds, hypertelorism, flat nose and receding chin.^[10] Although our patient's mother had oligohydramnios, the characteristic Potter facies was not present.

Sirenomelia can be diagnosed in the first trimester on prenatal ultrasound.^[1] In this case, prenatal ultrasound did not detect the lower limbs fusion and reports have shown that sonographic detection of sirenomelia can be limited by the presence of oligohydramnios.^[11] The most reliable confirmation for sirenomelia is postnatal radiograph and autopsy after birth.^[12] However, the utility of carrying babies with sirenomelia to term is a matter of contention. Treatment of sirenomelia is multidisciplinary, difficult and expensive and the outcome is guarded. An ethical dilemma exists on the benefit of treating such patients considering the multiple internal organs affected, the long term consequences and the quality of life even after treatment. Cultural beliefs and the likelihood of stigmatization leave the question of what exactly is best for babies with sirenomelia still a subject of debate till date.

CONCLUSIONS

Sirenomelia is usually fatal. Many pregnancies with a fetus having sirenomelia spontaneously miscarry. About fifty percent of infants with mermaid syndrome are stillborn, with most dying in the neonatal period usually from complications associated with abnormal kidney and bladder development and function. Preconception planning of pregnancy, early and regular prenatal care, effective glucose control and avoidance of teratogenic substances during pregnancy are recommended. It is our hope that this report would add to the existing knowledge and data about the condition and help reduce stigmatization of affected individuals and families.

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